

D4.2 WILSON use and business cases definition

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Short Description	
The deliverable describes the 8 representative WILSON use and business cases that will guide the development of WILSON tools and evaluate their innovation level, in particular through their implementation in the pilot sites. This activity is part of Work Package 4 (WP4).	

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ADR	Action Design Research
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMS	Building Management Systems
BPMN	Business Process Modelling and Notation
CAFM	Computer-Aided Facility Management
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DT	Digital Twin
DR	Demand Response
HEMS	Home Energy Management System
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
INN	Innovation
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LBD	Linked Building Data
LCA	Life-cycle assessment
LCC	Life-cycle Cost
PDH(s)	Personalised Building Data Hub(s)
RES	Renewable Energy Systems (or Sources)
ROI	Return on Investment
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
UCs	Use Cases
WP	Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The WILSON project, “Distributed Data Modelling and Federated Digital Twinning for Lifecycle Data-Driven Sustainable Operation and Management of Buildings and Districts,” aims to revolutionise building management through the development of advanced building and district digital twin technologies and innovative data integration strategies. This deliverable (D4.2) provides the work carried out in Task 4.2, through the development of the 8 representative use cases, which form the foundation for both the technical tool development and the exploration of new business models across pilot sites.

For the development of use cases, a structured, iterative methodology was adopted that combined the Action Design Research framework with the BS EN 62559-2:2015 use case modelling standard. Through two rounds of workshops and close collaboration with stakeholders – including technical development and pilot partners – the user requirements were identified and mapped to the main WILSON system functionalities. This approach ensured that the use cases not only address current challenges but also anticipate future development needs of WILSON across key built environment domains such as energy monitoring, predictive maintenance, resilience assessment, renovation planning and investment evaluation.

Key findings include the identification of 8 comprehensive use cases that underpin core system functionalities such as federated data management, digital twin integration, predictive and prescriptive analytics, blockchain-based marketplaces, and decision support for sustainable investments. These results highlight the potential of the proposed WILSON approach of leveraging decentralized data architectures and advanced analytics to drive real-time, data-driven decision-making in building and district management.

The outcomes of Task 4.2 provide the foundation for the development of WILSON data and interoperability innovations (WP5-8) and energy and non-energy tools (in WP9-12) that aim to improve operational efficiency and sustainability across buildings and districts. In addition, new opportunities for business models that can transform asset management and energy optimization practices across the built environment were identified, to be further developed at a later stage of the project (T15.3).

The development of the proposed use cases provides a valuable starting point for validation of WILSON tools across the 4 pilots, as well as the continued refinement of both technical and business requirements. This will ensure that the WILSON project not only meets its immediate objectives but also contributes to broader policy and market shifts towards sustainable, digitally enabled building management, in line with EU policy.

2. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents the 8 representative use cases for WILSON, including the adopted methodology for use case development and results, which define the main WILSON functionalities and will be used to guide the technical development of energy and non-energy applications and the exploration of new business models across pilot sites.

2.1. Scope of the deliverable

D4.2 provides the results of the work performed in T4.2. This deliverable provides the detailed description and rationale behind the use case methodology adopted to develop the 8 WILSON use cases, and the results of use case development. As outcomes of the development of use cases, the main system functionalities of WILSON are identified, as well as a set of potential business cases for pilot sites to be further developed in T15.3. Together with the work developed in T4.1, T4.2 provides the initial set of requirements to be considered for the development of the various WILSON data and interoperability innovations (WP5-8) and energy and non-energy tools (in WP9-12).

2.2. Structure of the deliverable

To fulfil the objectives of T4.2 “Analysis of use & business cases and definition of main system functionalities”, this deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 3 – Use case methodology:** Describes the methodology adopted for the development of use cases.
- **Section 4 – Use cases summary:** Provides an overview of the 8 WILSON use cases, including the scope, objectives, description, overview of the scenarios and overview BPMN diagrams. The detailed use case information including sub-process BPMN diagrams is provided in the ANNEXES section.
- **Section 5 – Use and business cases analysis:** Provides an overview of the initially identified business cases that will be further developed in T15.3, as well as the identification of main system functionalities.

2.3. Relation with other tasks and deliverables

The use cases developed in this task, combined with the other tasks in WP4, in particular T4.1, form the initial set of requirements to be considered during the development of WILSON data and interoperability innovations (WP5-8), as well as specific tool developments (energy and non-energy applications) in the WILSON project (WP9-12).

This task was developed in close collaboration to T4.1, considering the identified information requirements, which are referenced in the use cases. The baseline information requirements from the pilots are defined in detail in D4.1. Through the adoption of the BPMN, diagrams were developed to describe the use cases, including the interaction between actors and the information requirements. The developed diagrams will be considered in WP7, which will provide the service-oriented architecture to enable access to heterogeneous data streams via Personalised Data Hubs of built assets.

Finally, the identification of potential business models carried out by technical partners together with pilot partners will form the basis of the development of WILSON business models for pilot sites in T15.3.

3. USE CASE METHODOLOGY

Understanding user requirements and effectively translating them into functional features is crucial for the creation of digital twins of buildings and districts [1].

The use case methodology adopted in T4.2 supports the shared understanding of functionalities, actors, and processes of developed digital twin applications for buildings, building portfolios and complex embedded systems, across different organisations in the WILSON consortium and beyond.

Although there is no standard regarding the use case modelling for buildings and building portfolios, BS EN 62559-2:2015, an international standard defining template for use cases, actor list and requirement list for use case repository for Smart Grids applications [2], provides a good reference for the use case analysis in WILSON.

The use case methodology offers a unique way for sharing ideas and requirements of use cases and business cases between experts within different backgrounds and disciplines, e.g., domain experts with knowledge about predictive maintenance (UC4) on the one hand and system experts defining data exchange and communication on the other hand. In the requirement development process, domain experts provide general ideas and functional requirements, while system experts detail down these use cases to a level that can be used to specify interfaces, dedicated functionalities, data and service model exchange.

In order to develop descriptions of the requirements and functions for urban digital twins at building and district levels, a WILSON-specific use case methodology is designed by combining the Action Design Research framework proposed by Sein et al. [3] with the use case development defined in BS IEC SRD 62559-4:2020 [4]. The proposed use case methodology aims to address the following objectives:

- To develop a standard methodology for determining and defining user requirements in a consistent and comprehensive manner.
- To clarify the distinction between “user requirements” (the “what” as needed by WILSON demonstrations) and “technical specifications” (the “how” as technical descriptions of systems, applications, and information flows to meet the “what”).
- To emphasise the critical need to determine all user requirements first, before any commitments are made on “how” to meet those requirements. Because buildings, their embedded systems, and surrounding infrastructure are so complex and are becoming increasingly so, if all requirements are not clearly defined first, then the premature design of systems can block or seriously hinder meeting those requirements that were not initially recognised.
- To provide a means for testing the systems once implemented to ensure that the user requirements are truly met, regardless of what technologies are ultimately incorporated by the R&D partners and technological providers.

The Action Design Research (ADR) framework was adopted for the development of use cases in the WILSON project considering the requirements of WILSON pilot sites. The

development of use cases consists of a cyclical process of planning, action, observation and reflection. Use case development is coordinated by use case leaders, and two rounds of workshops were undertaken to confirm and review the scope of use cases, enabling iterative enhancements during the use case development process. The Action Design Research (ADR) framework adopted in WILSON is summarised in Table 1 and its stages and steps are detailed in the following sections.

Table 1 – Action design research for UC development

Stage 1 – Problem formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use cases proposed in the WILSON GA Use case scoping: Identification of UC leaders and stakeholders
Stage 2 – Building, intervention and evaluation – Use case development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial development of use cases Use case workshops (round 1) Further development of use cases Use case workshops (round 2)
Stage 3 – Reflection and learning – Developing detailed user requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop final version of use cases, and identification of business cases and main system functionalities
Stage 4 – Formalisation – Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reporting (D4.2)

3.1. Stage 1: Problem formulation

Identification of use case leaders and stakeholders: For each Use Case (UC) defined in WILSON, all domain experts and other stakeholders (users), that could impact or be impacted by the project were identified. Use Case leaders were identified – according to technical partners’ expertise – to coordinate the requirements gathering activities for each use case.

Once identified, all these stakeholders, including pilot partners, were consulted for user requirements that could impact (or be impacted by) the project. In this process, stakeholders were encouraged to think “out of the box”, to brainstorm future scenarios, and to envision new capabilities, rather than just restating existing functions. Table 2 provides an overview of the 8 WILSON use cases, use case leaders, participant partners, and frontrunner pilots.

Table 2 – Summary of use cases, use case leaders and participants

Use cases	Name	UC Leader	Participant partners	Frontrunner pilot
UC1	Decentralised multi-source data management	TUE	CIRCE, UNEW, CSTB, QUE, PARQ, WATTX, IDSA	UK
UC2	Energy monitoring and optimisation	CIRCE	SAK, CSTB, PARQ, WATTX	Spain
UC3	Data-driven network asset management	CIRCE	UNEW, CSTB, TUE, QUE, WATTX, IDSA	Switzerland

Use cases	Name	UC Leader	Participant partners	Frontrunner pilot
UC4	Predictive maintenance	UNEW	CIRCE, CSTB, TUE, QUE, WATTX	UK
UC5	Risk, resilience and biodiversity nexus	CSTB	CIRCE, RINA	Italy
UC6	Renovation planning and design	CSTB	CIRCE, TUE, RINA	Italy
UC7	Technoeconomic investment planning for property owners	GND	CIRCE, CSTB, PARQ, WATTX, UNEW	Spain
UC8	Boost of green energy investments by market actors	HSLU	CIRCE, WATTX	Switzerland

3.2. Stage 2: Building, intervention and evaluation – Use case development

Development of use cases: For each use case, UC leaders developed a list of functions in collaboration with the identified stakeholders – in particular considering pilot requirements and available data – to capture all user requirements associated with each UC. An iterative and stepwise refinement-based methodology was adopted during the requirements gathering process. Two rounds of use case development were undertaken. After each round, workshops were carried out with use case participants to refine the scope and objectives of the use cases and review progress. This approach facilitated the requirements gathering process by stimulating stakeholder interest, fostering collaboration during the process, and obtaining stakeholder buy-in (in particular from the pilots).

Use case workshops: Two rounds of workshops were conducted to support the development of the use cases. Use case leaders presented the status of each use case, followed by structured discussions focusing on use case development, focusing on:

- Confirmation of the scope and objectives of the use case
- Pre-requisites
- Participating actors/stakeholders
- Scenarios
- Information exchanges
- Identification of business cases linked to target objectives of the use case and main system functionalities

3.3. Stage 3: Reflection and learning – Developing detailed user requirements

Coordinate use cases and develop detailed user requirements: We coordinated the use cases from the R&D partners, technological providers, and pilot partners, and combined common components into “subroutine” use cases, while still maintaining the unique

components. For example, the “Multi-source Secure Data Access” scenario defined in UC1 (Decentralised multi-source data management) is used in other UCs, such as UCs 2, 3 & 6. Meanwhile, the list of actors recorded in the UCs typically contains many duplicates and many different names for the same actor. The various use case documents provided by use case leaders were examined to eliminate duplicate actors and scenarios, agree on common naming/terminology, and refine the scope of the UCs. This process was carried out initially after the first round of workshops, and once again after the final round of workshops to ensure that all requirements have been captured.

Use case diagrams: Use case diagrams provide a visual representation of the functional requirements of the system, which indicates buildings and surrounding infrastructure in the WILSON project. They help in understanding how users interact with a system and the various use cases or functionalities the system provides.

Business Process Modelling and Notation (BPMN), a standard proposed by the Object Management Group [5] was used for the development of the use case scenario diagrams. BPMN was adopted since it provides a clear representation for the collaboration between stakeholders in the use cases, through the clear definition of the role of each actor, and the exchanges of data/information.

BPMN diagrams developed in this task will also be used in WP7 as a starting point to identify services for the proposed service-oriented architecture, which will enable access to heterogeneous data streams via Personalised Data Hubs of built assets.

3.4. Stage 4: Formalisation – Reporting

The use case template proposed in BS EN 62559-2:2015 [2] was adopted to describe the 8 WILSON use cases (Figure 1). In section 4 USE CASES SUMMARY a summary of each use case is provided, including the scope and objectives, and an overview of scenarios. The detailed description of each use case, including the full description of actors, scenarios, information exchanges, and use case diagrams is provided in Section 7 – ANNEXES.

USE CASE TEMPLATE

In software and systems engineering, a use case is mostly a list of scenarios and steps, typically defining interactions between roles, i.e. actors and systems, to achieve a particular goal, e.g., a function. Actors can be human, components, or external systems.

In this way, documenting relations between functions, processes, and systems via use cases has proven to be rather successful for systems engineering. The BS EN/IEC 62559-2 template provides an adopted version of this concept for the smart grid area and has been the first area-specific initiative to document area-specific functional and non-functional requirements. In this task, we adapt the use case template to record the user requirements.

Figure 1 - Overview of the use case template

4. USE CASES SUMMARY

This section provides the summary of the 8 WILSON use cases (Table 2). An overview of each use case is provided, including the scope, objectives, description of the use case, as well as an overview of scenarios per use case, including overview BPMN diagrams. The detailed description of each use case, including the full description of actors, scenarios, information exchanges, and detailed BPMN diagrams is provided in Section 7 - ANNEXES. A summary of the BPMN elements used to elaborate the diagrams is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - BPMN elements adopted for use case modelling

4.1. UC1 - Decentralised multi-source data management

4.1.1. Scope

The scope of this use case limits to the data use within the Personalised Building Data Hubs (PDHs). WILSON will provide PDHs at both building and district level. Initially the scope of UC1 is limited to the building level and will be extended to the district level later.

4.1.2. Objectives

The objectives of Use case 1 - Decentralised multi-source data management are the following:

- Achieve interoperability among diverse data sources scattered across different platforms and formats.
- Facilitate real-time data integration for improved decision-making in building management (e.g., renovation, energy optimization).

- Enable decentralized control and management of building data using decentralized digital twins.

4.1.3. Description and scenarios overview

Decentralised multi-source data management includes the management of multiple data sources, e.g. databases, IoT streams, document stores, that are scattered across various platforms in a decentralised manner. Data from multiple places are to be transferred and transformed to Personalised Building Data Hubs (PDHs), one per building. For an end user, multiple PDHs are available, leading to multi-source data access. The PDHs are configured in a decentralised manner, namely without central control. This means that these multi-source data can be accessed from a number of places in a non-central manner.

By leveraging a federated DT approach, the system enables end users to access reliable, real-time building data from multiple systems, simplifying energy monitoring, planning, circularity decisions, and overall building management. The decentralized data mesh architecture fosters data accessibility and ownership, promoting direct connections between data owners, producers, and consumers. This novel approach goes beyond traditional data lakes, treating data as a product and enabling self-serve data platforms. Leveraging existing ontologies from the community-based Linked Building Data (LBD) efforts (including IFC) enhances machine-readability and interoperability, providing a comprehensive solution for managing and integrating data in district digital twins, catering to stakeholders and their unique needs in different domains (e.g., buildings, transportation, utilities). An overview of scenarios for UC1 is provided in Table 3. BPMN diagrams for both scenarios are provided in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively.

Table 3 – Overview of scenarios – UC1 - Decentralised multi-source data management

Scenario name	Scenario description
Multi-source secure data access	Centralized secure data access system allows authorized users to access relevant data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verify and confirm user identity and permissions using multi-factor authentication (MFA). • Deliver relevant data to the end user in a secure format while logging the transaction for compliance.
Data Storage and Archiving	Secure and organized method for storing and archiving multi-source data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect, store and organize data (e.g., sensor data, BIM models, energy data) locally in secure, compliant storage systems for each source – considering short & long term data uses. • Data categorisation, archiving and logging: Encrypt data, implement access control, and regularly review and audit archived data to ensure data integrity, updating and migrating formats as needed to prevent data degradation

Figure 3 - UC1 - Multi-source secure data access

Figure 4 - UC1 - Data Storage and Archiving

4.2. UC2 - Energy monitoring and optimisation

4.2.1. Scope

The scope of UC2 is to seeks to optimise energy consumption in buildings and portfolios through real-time monitoring, AI and demand response strategies. It prioritises efficiency,

occupant comfort and environmental sustainability, integrating IoT, BMS and renewable energy to reduce costs and minimise the carbon footprint.

4.2.2. Objectives

The objectives of Use case 2 - Energy monitoring and optimisation are the following:

- Optimise energy performance: Reduce operating costs through the implementation of energy efficiency solutions thus allowing a more intelligent use of resources
- Improve the user comfort: Ensure optimal lighting, ventilation and temperature, adjusting them dynamically
- Enhance environmental sustainability: Reduce the building's carbon footprint, decrease pollution and excessive use of resource.

4.2.3. Description and scenarios overview

This use case focuses on optimising energy management at both building and portfolio levels, empowering key actors (such as property owners) to make data-driven decisions to enhance energy performance, comfort, and environmental sustainability. WILSON toolset integrates cutting-edge technologies and data analytics, enabling smart energy monitoring and control systems to track HVAC and lighting consumption, among others. Additionally, DR mechanisms adjust energy usage during peak demand periods, and RES systems are seamlessly integrated into the system for real-time monitoring. Occupant well-being and comfort-as-a-service are prioritised through occupancy sensors and user feedback, allowing dynamic adjustments to environmental factors. WILSON also facilitates environmental sustainability by tracking energy performance, carbon emissions, and environmental impact while implementing energy-saving practices.

The optimisation of energy management use case is divided into these sequences:

- **Critical asset identification and clustering:** The most critical assets and areas are identified and clustered into categories. This clustering enables more efficient monitoring, allowing optimisation to be applied more accurately to avoid critical failures that may impact the normal operation of the system. for the application of optimization adjust the process.
- **Data acquisition:** Data from IoT, BMS and other installed devices and manufacturer specifications, is collected.
- **Optimisation modelling for energy management:** Machine learning algorithms are applied to model to improve energy performance, comfort and environmental sustainability. This toolset integrates cutting-edge technologies and data analytics, enabling smart energy monitoring and control systems to track HVAC and lighting consumption, among others.
- **Execution of optimisation and validation processes:** Based on the insights obtained, optimization tasks are designed to maximise comfort and reduce consumption. The execution involves the deployment of the necessary equipment for monitoring, as

well as corroborating the correct relationship between comfort and energy consumption.

An overview of the scenarios identified in UC 2 is provided in Table 4. The overview BPMN diagram for the use case is provided in Figure 5.

Table 4 - Overview of scenarios – UC2 - Energy monitoring and optimisation

Scenario name	Scenario description
Data acquisition and database	Collect data from IoT sensors and BMS and organize it and its history in a database.
Execute Optimisation Strategies	AI and math algorithms that adjust and optimize the consumption model of building .and energy community
Make Predictions	Machine learning algorithms that Forecast the usage of energy within the building.
Show Future Analytics	Predictions and analysis of data is shown on interface to user
Assets Integration	Assets are integrated within building by System Operators
Model Creation	Developers create prediction and optimisation models.
Maintain Operations within Building	Assets are checked regularly in search of any kind of failure and/or problem.

Figure 5 - UC2 - Energy monitoring and optimisation

4.3. UC3 - Data-driven network asset management

4.3.1. Scope

The scope of this UC is to develop advanced tools to optimise network asset management through Digital Twins and data analysis. It allows for predicting the useful life of assets,

anticipating failures and defining risk-based strategies, improving operational efficiency and network resilience through the integration of IoT, historical and geospatial data.

4.3.2. Objectives

The objectives of Use case 3 – Data-driven network asset management are the following:

- Optimise network performance: Reduce operating costs by implementing efficient solutions that enable the Digital Twin network to operate correctly.
- Improve proactive prediction of asset life and expected failures: Ensure the correct use of equipment and systems to enable correct failure prediction and maintenance.
- Provide comprehensive insight into network assets with information from smart meters, historical failures, network asset data, and geo-spatial data
- Predict asset life and anticipate failures by integrating this data into DT network.
- Allow the definition of risk-based asset management strategies with failure probabilities, criticality indexing and device health indexing.

4.3.3. Description and scenarios overview

This Use Case offers network operators advanced, data-driven tools to optimise asset management and enhance network resilience. By integrating diverse data into network DTs, operators can proactively predict asset lifespans and potential failures. This enables reliability planning and risk-based strategies using failure probabilities and asset health indexing.

The Data-driven network asset management optimisation use case is divided into following sequences:

- **Critical asset identification and clustering:** The most critical assets and areas are identified and clustered into categories. This clustering enables more efficient monitoring, allowing optimization to be applied more accurately to avoid critical failures that may impact the normal operation of the system.
- **Data acquisition:** Data from IoT, BMS and other installed device and manufacturer specifications, and other data like the use of smart metering data from prosumers, historical failures, network asset data, visual and IR imagery, and geo-spatial data to provide comprehensive insights into network assets.
- **Optimization of Data-driven network asset management:** Focuses on the use of the DT network as a tool for modelling, analysing and predicting the behaviour of infrastructure asset in real time.
- **Execution Digital Twin implementation and proactive prediction:** Based on the knowledge gained, the Digital Twin network is optimised. The system enables proactive prediction of asset lifetime and expected failures, facilitating reliability planning and identifying common causes of asset failures.

An overview of the scenarios identified in UC 3 is provided in Table 5. The overview BPMN diagram for the use case is provided in Figure 6.

Table 5 – Overview of scenarios – UC3 – Data-driven network asset management

Scenario name	Scenario description
Data acquisition and integration	Collect and integrate data from IoT sensors, BMS, cameras and manufacturer specifications.
DT Network Creation	Create Digital Twin network, integrate a virtual model and develop a digital model representing the entire network infrastructure with decentralised implementation
Optimisation of demand management and energy trading	Implement blockchain to create a decentralised framework that allows users to participate in data and service transactions between participants and receive remuneration accordingly.
Prediction of Asset Life	Prediction of Asset Life focuses on analysing, optimising and predicting the useful life of each asset based on historical data and specifications in order to prevent DT network failures
Visualization of failure prediction and prevention	Predicting potential failures in network assets using data-driven analysis from the DT.
Critical Asset Identification and Clustering	The most critical assets for the overall operation of the network are grouped according to their importance, operational characteristics or strategic location. This allows focusing maintenance efforts and resources on the most relevant elements.
Implement Asset Management Strategies	Asset management strategies based on data analysis and criticality prioritization. Implementation includes preventive maintenance and corrective and infrastructure adjustments to minimize risks and optimize network performance.
Manager Flexibility Asset	Manage the operational flexibility of network assets to respond to variations in demand, network conditions or unforeseen events. To maximize the efficient use of available resources, minimising outages and ensuring network stability.

Figure 6 - UC3 - Data-driven network asset management

4.4. UC4 – Predictive maintenance

4.4.1. Scope

Predictive maintenance prioritises the repair and replacement of critical assets in buildings and building portfolios to reduce the downtime and consequent disturbance to occupants.

4.4.2. Objectives

The objectives of Use case 4 – Predictive maintenance are the following:

- Minimise facility downtime: Reduce unexpected equipment failures by predicting potential issues before they occur, thus minimising the downtime of critical building assets.
- Improve occupant experience: Ensure continuous operation of essential services (e.g., HVAC, elevators) to reduce disruption and maintain comfort and safety for building occupants.
- Optimise maintenance costs: Decrease the overall maintenance costs by moving from reactive to predictive maintenance, ensuring that repairs are done only when necessary and extending the lifespan of assets.
- Enhance Asset Management: Improve the decision-making process regarding asset replacement and repair by using data-driven insights, leading to more efficient management of building portfolios.

4.4.3. Description and scenarios overview

The predictive maintenance use case is divided into four sequences:

- **Critical asset identification and clustering:** The most critical assets are identified and clustered into categories based on their type and operation conditions. This clustering enables more efficient monitoring by grouping similar assets together, allowing for the application of targeted predictive maintenance strategies.
- **Data acquisition:** Data from IoT sensors, BMS, historical maintenance records (CAFM), and manufacturer specifications, is collected.
- **Deterioration modelling and failure prediction:** Machine learning algorithms are applied to model the patterns of asset deterioration and predict failures and maintenance needs.
- **Maintenance prioritisation and execution:** Based on the insights gained, maintenance tasks are scheduled at optimal times to minimise disruption. The execution involves deploying maintenance teams to perform the necessary repairs or replacements according to the prioritisation.

An overview of the scenarios identified in UC4 is provided in Table 6. The overview BPMN diagram for the use case is provided in Figure 7.

Table 6 - Overview of scenarios – UC4 - Predictive maintenance

Scenario name	Scenario description
Asset inventory review	Generate a comprehensive list of asset inventory for each building.
Critical asset identification	Identify key assets critical to safety, operations, and occupant comfort.
Asset clustering	Categorise assets based on type (e.g., HVAC, electrical systems, plumbing), and group assets by operational conditions (e.g., high-use areas, harsh environments).
Data acquisition and integration	Collect and integrate data from IoT sensors, BMS, historical maintenance records (CAFM), and manufacturer specifications.
Asset deterioration modelling	Machine learning algorithms are applied to model asset deterioration patterns and predict failures and maintenance needs.
Maintenance scheduling	Schedule maintenance tasks based on predictive insights to minimise disruption and ensure asset reliability.
Maintenance execution	Deploy maintenance teams to perform repairs or replacements according to the scheduled tasks.

Figure 7 – UC4 - Predictive maintenance

4.5. UC5 – Risk, resilience and biodiversity nexus

4.5.1. Scope

The scope of UC5 is to improve the methodologies to assess the risk, the resilience and the environmental (carbon & biodiversity) performance for new buildings and deep renovations' planning and design processes.

4.5.2. Objectives

The objective of UC5 is to propose science-based methods to assess risk, resilience and environmental indicators & KPIs for decision-aid.

4.5.3. Description and scenarios overview

The risk, resilience (to climate change) and environmental performance of buildings and district is a huge challenge and appropriate methods, indicators and KPI are necessary for the decision-aid. That implies the development of sciences-based methods that could be

apply in different European countries, by considering the European standards, the local specificities, the available input data needed for the calculation and the equilibrium between the effort to calculate the indicators /KPI and the results obtained, i.e. the assessment efficiency.

The UC 5 is divided in 3 main steps:

- **Resilience assessment and analysis**, divided into the following steps:
 - Integrated Risk and Resilience Assessment: RINA provides tools for evaluating vulnerabilities, risks, and resilience indicators throughout an asset's lifecycle, integrating risk management, crisis management, and business continuity into asset management processes,
 - Scenario and Hazard Analysis: The platform enables users to model and quantify risks, analyse hazards (natural or man-made), and visualize impacts through customizable scenarios that include spatial and temporal distributions,
 - Data-Driven Decision Support: The platform delivers outputs such as loss curves, resilience matrices, and expected annual loss estimations to guide resource allocation, prioritize investments, and optimize lifecycle costs,
 - Use Case-Specific Applications: The analysis is tailored to specific use cases, ranging from seismic, floods and heatwaves analysis of resilience to maintenance planning and emergency response optimization;
- **Climate change resilience** focusing on the UHI mitigation, microclimate modelling approach will be used to assess the as-is and alternative scenarios for the WILSON pilots and to provide a method that could be replicated on other buildings and districts; the performance of each scenario will be assessed based on the indicators & KPI defined in T4.5;
- **Environmental assessment including the biodiversity**, carried out based on the LCA to provide indicators/KPI on climate change mitigation; the biodiversity issues are tackled on both on site (Biodiversity in situ) and global scale (Biodiversity ex - situ) based on the HIBOU method (INN6)

An overview of the scenarios identified in UC5 is provided in Table 7. The overview BPMN diagram for the use case is provided in Figure 8.

Table 7 - Overview of scenarios – UC5 - Risk, resilience and biodiversity nexus

Scenario name	Scenario description
Asset, Context and Hazards Characterization	Input data gathering for each demo site/pilot (incl. data from national regulatory entities) - Definition of the proxy / generic data to be use for the calculation step based on the state of the art
Risk, Resilience, Carbon and Biodiversity Assessment	Create as-is model and to-be model
Data-Driven Decision Support	Once the state of the art has been evaluated, improvements are implemented to evaluate the asset's behaviour

Use Applications	Case-Specific	mitigation of the risks arising from hazards, assess the carbon and biodiversity impacts and proposing actions aimed at improving KPI related to the use case
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Figure 8 - UC5 - Risk, resilience and biodiversity nexus

4.6. UC6 - Renovation planning and design

4.6.1. Scope

UC6 applies methodologies to assess environmental (carbon & biodiversity) and economic performance integrating circular economy principles into the deep renovations planning and design process.

4.6.2. Objectives

The main objective of UC6 is to propose a cutting-edge WILSON planning and design toolkit that enables efficient building renovation conceptualization in accordance with European standards.

4.6.3. Description and scenarios overview

Building renovation design using IT services involves a systematic approach that leverages technology to streamline the process and enhance efficiency.

The overall approach follows the workflow:

- **Define project scope and goals:** gather building information, define project goals, and identify constraints.
- **Data collection and analysis:** using BIM and proxy data when BIM is not available, energy performance analysis, and environmental impact assessment.

- **Design renovation alternatives:** create and evaluate alternative design concepts while integrating sustainability principles.
- **Validate concept and proceed to technical design:** Ensure compliance with codes and regulations, obtain permits, and engage stakeholders. Then, create detailed drawings, schedule the project, and estimate costs.

Building renovation design, facilitated by Wilson's IT services, is a streamlined process that leverages technology to enhance efficiency and sustainability. This approach employs a systematic methodology that leverages technology to optimize the building renovation process, ensuring enhanced efficiency and sustainability.

The renovation use case involves gathering building information, defining project goals, and identifying constraints before collecting and analysing data using BIM and proxy when BIM is not available, energy performance analysis, and environmental impact assessment. Design concepts are then created while integrating sustainability principles and ensuring compliance with codes, regulations, and stakeholder engagement. Detailed drawings, project scheduling, and cost estimation follow (out of scope). Wilson's tools, which include cost-benefit analysis and standardization aspects, support comprehensive planning and design of energy-efficient renovations and retrofitting projects. These tools assess environmental and economic performance, align with digitalization trends, and implement EU standards. Building owners can use these tools to plan deep renovations, centralize building information, and gain a comprehensive overview of the building's lifecycle, integrating circular economy principles.

An overview of the scenarios identified in UC6 is provided in Table 8. The overview BPMN diagram for the use case is provided in Figure 9.

Table 8 - Overview of scenarios – UC6 - Renovation planning and design

Scenario name	Scenario description
Project scope, Budget, and Contractors	Purely human activity: envisioning the renovation project, defining the scope and objectives, allocating the budget, and identifying the contractors.
Gather as-is data	Activity of collecting and storing documents, BIM data, and any information describing the initial state of the building to be renovated (as-is).
Create as-is model	The data collected on the original building is used to create the first digital twin model, which represents the as-built situation and is used in subsequent processes.
Improve As-Is Model	Improve the level of detail of the digital twin to capture more accurate information about the existing building. Data from building stock databases and product catalogues can be used to improve the initial description of the situation.
Design of possible alternatives	Different renovation alternatives can be designed using different products from product catalogues. Different passports can be created for these different alternatives.

Process Baseline, Alternatives & Update Passports	Various simulation tools use DT semantic descriptions and the various values from the created passports to calculate and store KPIs for the "as-is" baseline situation and for the various alternatives that have been created.
Validate Concept: Choose an Alternative	Displaying calculated KPIs, enabling the technical team and client to make an informed decision on the preferred renovation alternative.
Validate project	Regulatory bodies can validate the refurbishment project and issue all necessary permits.
Technical Phase Design	A more detailed technical design is created for the chosen renovation option, preparing for the execution phase

Figure 9 - UC6 - Renovation planning and design

4.7. UC7 - Technoeconomic investment planning for property owners

4.7.1. Scope

UC7 focuses on delivering an investment planning tool that allows property owners and stakeholders to assess the financial and environmental feasibility of building renovation projects. The tool will evaluate economic aspects such as ROI, payback periods, and property value enhancements, as well as environmental benefits such as carbon footprint reduction and energy efficiency improvements.

4.7.2. Objectives

The objectives of UC7 - Technoeconomic investment planning for property owners are the following:

- Support investors' and property owners' decision-making process
- Integrate technical factors (such as energy efficiency improvements, reduced operational costs, etc.) with economical ones (such as increased property value, associated upfront expenses)
- Provide stakeholders with comprehensive insights aiding their decision-making processes regarding operation and planned investments
- Support the development of new business models
- Cater to a vast audience of sustainable energy investors, boosting the project's outreach even post-completions

4.7.3. Description and scenarios overview

This use case involves the creation of a technoeconomic investment tool that analyses building upgrade options based on lifecycle cost assessments, environmental impact metrics, and financial indicators. It leverages detailed data on building performance, energy consumption, maintenance costs, and environmental impact to project potential savings and ROI. The tool includes scenario-based modelling for renovations, enabling stakeholders to compare investment scenarios, optimize cost-effectiveness, and align with sustainability standards. The overall process involves:

- **Assessing existing building performance**, including energy consumption, costs, maintenance needs, and environmental impact
- **Identifying investment opportunities** like energy-efficient systems and building automation
- **Technological evaluations of each opportunity**
- **Cost Benefit analysis (CBA)** to assess financial implications
- **LCC evaluation** for long-term viability and risk analysis, alongside environmental impact assessment
- **Financial modelling** to simulate different investment scenarios

An overview of the scenarios identified in UC7 is provided in Table 9. The overview BPMN diagram for the use case is provided in Figure 10.

Table 9 - Overview of scenarios – UC7 – Technoeconomic investment planning for property owners

Scenario name	Scenario description
Assessment of the building	Assess existing building performance
Identification of investment opportunities	Identify all relevant possible investment opportunities that can be tailored to the needs of the construction of new buildings
Cost-benefit analysis	Conduct Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) to assess financial implications
LCC evaluation	Evaluate Life Cycle Cost implication for long-term viability
Financial modelling	Simulate different investment scenarios with financial modelling

Figure 10 - UC7 - Technoeconomic investment planning

4.8. UC8 - Boost of green energy investments by market actors

4.8.1. Scope

The scope of UC8 is Energy Monitoring for Distribution System Operators (DSOs). It is enabling green energy investments by integrating building data sources and optimizing DSO operations and investments through grid load monitoring and simulation.

4.8.2. Objectives

The objectives of UC8 - Boost of green energy investments by market actors are the following:

- Establish a data space infrastructure to enable the monitoring of various building assets (e.g., smart meters, PV loggers, PV inverters, energy management systems, heat pumps) and external data sources.
- Provide an Energy Monitoring System for: (1) monitoring and forecasting energy consumption and production; (2) managing self-consumption optimization on a

building and energy community level; (3) simulating grid load; and (4) providing network capability metrics.

- Provide decision-making support for optimizing DSO operations and investments (e.g., congestion management, optimization and trading), based on network capabilities metrics.

4.8.3. Description and scenarios overview

This use case (UC8) introduces an Energy Monitoring System designed for Distribution System Operators (DSOs), leveraging a data space infrastructure to collect data from various building assets, including smart meters, PV loggers, PV inverters, heat pumps, and home energy management systems (HEMS) and external data sources - all without requiring additional hardware installations. By utilizing the data space for unified data access, the solution streamlines operations while ensuring data ownership and security.

Beyond the data space infrastructure, a key component of this use case is the Energy Monitoring System, which enables DSOs to:

- **Monitor and forecast energy consumption and production,**
- **Optimize self-consumption,**
- **Simulate grid load,** and
- **Provide network capability metrics.**

The primary objective is to equip DSOs with a decision-support tool that enhances energy monitoring, enabling informed decision-making to optimize operations and investments (e.g. peak shaving, congestion management, voltage stability, optimization and trading, reducing costs for balancing energy). The decision-making process is driven by network capability metrics supplied by the energy monitoring system.

An overview of the scenarios identified in UC8 is provided in Table 10. The overview BPMN diagram for the use case is provided in Figure 11.

Table 10 - Overview of scenarios – UC8 - Boost of green energy investments by market actors

Scenario name	Scenario description
Data access and collection using a data space infrastructure	Access and collect data from monitoring devices via a data space infrastructure.
Energy consumption and production monitoring	Collect the energy consumption and production data from the monitoring devices
Energy consumption	Forecast future energy consumption and production, based on the monitored data, as well as external data including weather forecast & consumer behaviour data.

and production forecasting	
Self-consumption optimization	AI and math algorithms that adjust and optimize the self-consumption of energy on building and community levels
Grid load simulation	AI and math algorithms that simulate the grid load on an energy community level based on the energy consumption of one or more buildings combined with external data in order to optimize simulations.
Network capability metrics provision	AI and math algorithms that provide network capability metrics
Show decision-support	Results of the Energy Monitoring System are shown in a GUI to provide decision-support
Self-consumption operations optimization	Decision-making to optimize self-consumption operations
Grid operations optimizations	Decision-making to optimize grid operations
Investment guidance	Decision-making to guide investments

Figure 11 - UC8 - Boost of green energy investments by market actors

5. USE AND BUSINESS CASES ANALYSIS

This section provides the analysis of the use and business cases and definition of main WILSON system functionalities.

The goal is to identify the potential business value of the use cases in particular considering the requirements of the pilot sites.

5.1. Identification of business cases

This section provides the initial identification of business cases to be used as a basis of the development of WILSON business models (T15.3), and their mapping to each of the 8 representative WILSON use cases. The proposed business cases were developed in collaboration between technical and pilot partners and coordinated by the UC leaders.

5.1.1. Data-Driven Decision Making and Interoperability (UC1, UC2, UC3, UC6)

General benefits:

- Enhanced decision - making through a “single source of truth”, improved data quality and governance, and improved integration with existing BMS, IoT and legacy systems.
- Streamlined decision-making for deep renovations, reduced renovation costs through optimized planning, and a clear pathway to energy-efficient, sustainable building upgrades.

Use Case benefits:

- **UC1 – Decentralised Multi-Source Data Management:** Implement a federated data management service that ingests, harmonises, and secures data from disparate building management systems and legacy sources. The platform uses a digital twin framework to enable real - time access and interoperability while preserving data ownership.
- **UC2 – Energy Monitoring and Optimisation:** Support the monitoring of real-time consumption and automatic adjustment of parameters to maximize energy efficiency without compromising comfort, as well as decision-making for deep renovations and sustainable building upgrades.
- **UC3 – Data-Driven Network Asset Management:** Leverages predictive analytics for asset management and creates opportunities (e.g., energy flexibility, digital energy communities) that support informed operational decisions (using DT and predictive algorithms developed in UC3).
- **UC6 – Renovation Planning and Design:** Create a digital platform that consolidates building design, operation, and life cycle data—including LCA metrics and material passport information—to support comprehensive renovation planning. This tool assists stakeholders in comparing different retrofit scenarios with built-in cost-benefit analyses.

5.1.2. Operational Efficiency and Sustainability (UC1, UC2, UC4, UC5)

General benefits:

Improve day-to-day building performance by optimising energy usage, enhancing maintenance practices, and integrating sustainability and risk management measures:

- Minimised downtime, extended asset life, and reduced operational costs through proactive maintenance scheduling.
- Better preparedness for climate hazards, optimized investment in resilience measures, and reduced long-term risk exposure.

Use Case benefits:

- **UC1 – Decentralised Multi-Source Data Management:** The federated data management approach provides real - time access to the various data sources used in the business case, while preserving data ownership.
- **UC2 – Energy Monitoring and Optimisation:** Implement an energy management system that optimizes the use of HVAC, lighting, and other critical hospital systems. The system would monitor real-time consumption and automatically adjust parameters to maximize efficiency without compromising comfort.
- **UC4 – Predictive Maintenance:** Deploy a service that continuously monitors asset performance using digital twin models and predictive analytics. The service forecasts remaining useful life (RUL) and triggers maintenance alerts before failures occur.
- **UC5 – Risk, Resilience and Biodiversity Nexus:** Offer a dynamic decision-support tool that quantifies building and district-level vulnerabilities using multi-criteria risk and resilience indicators (including Level of Service metrics). This service leverages lifecycle data to simulate various climate and operational scenarios.

5.1.3. Financial Optimisation and Investment Planning (UC7, UC8)

General Benefits: Deliver data-driven financial insights that lower investment risk, increase attractiveness of sustainable building upgrades to equity funds and property owners, and foster transparent, efficient investment marketplaces for sustainable projects.

Use Case benefits:

- **UC7 – Technoeconomic Investment Planning for Property Owners:** Provide a decision-support service that integrates energy performance data, predictive maintenance insights, and risk analysis to evaluate the economic feasibility of energy improvements and renovations. The tool uses life cycle cost (LCC) and return on investment (ROI) models to assess different scenarios.
- **UC8 – Boost of Green Energy Investments by Market Actors:** Provide a simulation-based platform that uses digital twin data and network planning algorithms to assess the feasibility and performance of renewable energy (RES) consumption, production and storage. The tool models demand and generation uncertainties and offers scenario ranking based on cost-efficiency for grid stability as well as energy trading.

5.1.4. Decentralised and Smart Energy Management (UC3, UC8)

General Benefits: Enable agile, decentralised energy solutions that balance real-time demand–supply, integrate renewable energy and storage, and leverage smart technologies for efficient energy planning.

Use Case benefits:

- **UC3 – Energy Flexibility Market:** A local energy flexibility market can be created to optimize demand and supply management in real time. Customers could participate by providing flexibility by reducing or increasing consumption according to the needs of the grid, through blockchain-based smart contracts.
- **UC8 – Blockchain-enabled Energy Investment Marketplace:** Establish a blockchain-enabled marketplace that connects DSOs, ESCOs, and investors to support transactions in energy services. Smart contracts facilitate secure, transparent investment and revenue-sharing models for projects in RES and storage.

5.2. Identification of main system functionalities

Following the analysis of the identified WILSON use and business cases, it is possible to identify the mapping between UCs, INNs and identify the main WILSON system functionalities (Table 11). Additional details for WILSON INNs are provided in D4.1.

Table 11 - Mapping between WILSON INNs, UCs and main system functionalities

WILSON Innovation (INN)	Use Cases	Main System Functionalities
INN1: District Digital Twins – Federation and Data Mesh	UC1, UC2, UC3, UC4	Digital Twin & Semantic Data Integration and Federated Data Management – Providing a unified, near real-time view of building and district data
INN2: Personalised Building Data Hubs (PDHs)	UC1, UC2, UC3, UC5	Federated Data Management and Digital Twin Integration – Enabling dynamic access and control over building data
INN3: P2P Data and Services Marketplace	UC1, UC3, UC8	Blockchain-based Marketplace for Data and Services – Facilitating transparent, secure transactions and service monetisation
INN4: Semantic-Aware Analytics Energy Management Toolset	UC2, UC3, UC6, UC8	Predictive & Prescriptive Analytics – Delivering actionable insights for energy and operational optimization

INN5: CIMBA – Predictive Maintenance	UC3, UC4	Predictive Analytics & Decision Support for Maintenance – Anticipating failures and optimizing maintenance scheduling
INN6: HIBOU – Biodiversity & Nature Based Solutions (NBS) in the urban systems	UC5, UC6	Resilience & Sustainability Assessment – Informing strategies for risk mitigation and sustainable building operations
INN7: CONTINIUM: centralised data repository for material passport	UC6, UC7	Decision Support for Renovation & Circular Economy Modelling – Optimizing renovation strategies and material reuse
INN8: Risk and Resilience Assessment	UC5, UC7	Resilience Assessment & Investment Decision Support – Enabling proactive risk management and resilience planning
INN9: BIM-Enabled Smart Readiness Indicator Calculator	UC6, UC7	Decision Support for Investments & Renovation – Providing key performance insights for energy efficiency upgrades

In summary, the main identified WILSON system functionalities are:

Federated Data Management & Digital Twin Integration:

Achieved through UC1, and underpinning UC2-UC8, these functionalities aim to ensure interoperability across data sources and provide a unified, real-time view of buildings and districts performance.

Predictive & Prescriptive Analytics:

Achieved through UC3 and UC4, these tools aim to support energy optimization, predictive maintenance, and informed decision-making.

Blockchain-Based Marketplace:

Achieved through UC3 and UC8, the Blockchain-Based Marketplace aims to facilitate secure, decentralized transactions for data and services, enabling new revenue models and energy flexibility markets.

Resilience & Sustainability Assessment:

Driven by UC5 and UC7, this functionality aims to empower stakeholders to evaluate risk, assess resilience, and integrate biodiversity and circular economy aspects.

Decision Support for Investments & Renovations:

This functionality is covered in UC6 and UC7 and aims to provide actionable insights and technoeconomic analysis to support renovation planning and investment decisions.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable provided the definition of the 8 use cases that encapsulate both the technical and business aspects of sustainable building and district management. Through the adoption of a structured, iterative use case methodology, this task (T4.2) has successfully captured critical user requirements, mapped these to system functionalities, and identified potential business models for future development.

The developed use cases consider the main WILSON objectives – to integrate heterogeneous data through federated digital twin technologies, enable real-time energy optimization and predictive maintenance, and support resilient, sustainable decision-making. Use case development considered decentralized data management and semantic data integration to bridge existing data silos, as well as advanced analytics and blockchain-enabled services to pave the way for innovative, market-driven solutions.

The main achievements of Task 4.2 can be summarised:

- Clear definition of use cases that cover all areas of WILSON developments from energy monitoring to technoeconomic investment planning.
- The mapping of these use cases to main system functionalities such as predictive analytics, resilience assessment, and decision support for renovations/investments planning.
- The adoption of a collaborative and iterative use case development methodology provided engagement with stakeholders, which enriched the use case definitions and ensured alignment with both pilot and technological requirements.

Lessons learned emphasize the importance of cross-disciplinary collaboration between technical, R&D and pilot partners and iterative design-approaches that have not only enhanced the overall quality of the use case development but also highlighted the necessity of agile responses to evolving stakeholder needs.

The use cases defined in this task will be used to validate subsequent WILSON developments, in particular, in DT enabled lifecycle data solutions for energy and non-energy uses in WP10 and WP12, respectively (due in October 2026), in the preparation for pilot implementations in WP13 (due in September 2027), in the large-scale demonstration activities in WP14 (due in February 2028), and finally in Task 15.3 “Development of business models and path-to-finance” in WP15 (due in April 2028). As such, use cases will be published and further explained in the deliverables of these WPs.

Future research should explore further integration of digital twin technologies with policy frameworks, promoting scalability and regulatory compliance. Additionally, the large-scale demonstration campaign in the 4 pilots will be crucial for fine-tuning the proposed WILSON innovations and demonstrating their economic and environmental benefits.

7. ANNEXES

7.1. UC1 - Decentralised multi-source data management

Table 12 – UC1 conditions

Assumptions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The building portfolio includes various processes and devices linked to building data management. This can be sensors, such as IoT devices, historical data, and BMS. This can also be a collection of various data models such as 3D models, point clouds and documents for multiple building elements, e.g. in the case of renovation. Building stakeholders are open to sharing data in a decentralized manner.
Prerequisites
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Buildings must have data available. A building should exist (e.g. UC1 is of less use in an early design phase).

Table 13 – UC1 Relationship to other use cases

Relationship to other use cases
Energy Monitoring and Optimization (UC2) Data-Driven Network Asset Management (UC3) Predictive Maintenance (UC4) Renovation Planning and Design (UC6)

Table 14 – UC1 Actors

Grouping		Group description	
PDH Systems		Systems supporting data integration, analysis, and usage within buildings and districts DT.	
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description	Further information specific to this use case
IoT devices	Device	Collects real-time building data, such as energy consumption, temperature, occupancy.	Data feeds into PDHs for further analysis.
Data Ingestion Software	System	Software that can ingest building models, e.g. 3D BIM models, point cloud models, files, etc.	Model data is loaded and ingested using an Extract-Transform-Load (ETL) procedure, that can include data transformations.
Building Model Database	Database/ Dataspace	Database with all building model data	One database per and each system in that building

Historical Database	Database/ Dataspace	Historical database that keeps track of all historical building data	One database per building and each system in that building
Authentication System	System	Verifies user credentials and permissions using MFA.	Generates authentication tokens for secure access.
Secure Data Access System	Database/ Dataspace	Manages secure access to aggregated data and logs transactions for compliance.	Handles aggregation and secure transmission of multi-source data.
Local Storage Systems	Database/ Dataspace	Stores data securely at the local level after collection.	Ensures encrypted storage and compliance with defined protocols.
Archive Storage System	Database/ Dataspace	Handles secure long-term data archiving, ensuring accessibility and compliance.	Supports isolated access to infrequently used data.
Compliance and Audit Systems	System	Reviews and audits archived data to ensure compliance and integrity.	Maintains logs and generates integrity reports.

Table 15 - UC1 References

Reference type	Reference	Impact on use case
Standard	ISO 19650 [6]	Standardized data formats for building data.
Service Contracts	Service Level Agreements (SLAs)	SLAs for building data services (e.g., IoT maintenance contracts)
International Framework	ISO/IEC 27001 [7]	Ensuring PDHs data integrity and security
Regulation	EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [8]	Ensures that personal data (e.g., energy consumption, occupancy data) is handled according to data privacy regulations.

Table 16 - UC1 Scenarios description

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
1	Multi-source	Centralized secure	End Users	Requests access to	Multi-factor authentication	User gains

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
	secure data access	data access system allows authorized users to access relevant data		data from multiple sources		access to relevant data
2	Data Storage and Archiving	Secure and organized method for storing and archiving multi-source data	Data Owners	Data collection completed	Data categorization protocols are defined	Data is securely stored and archived

Table 17 - UC1 Information exchanges

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
InfEx-1	Authentication Tokens	Secure tokens generated after successful multi-factor authentication.	No
InfEx-2	User Permission Details	Detailed permissions for accessing data sources, specific to the user's role.	No
InfEx-3	Aggregated Data from Sources	Combined data from IoT devices, GIS systems, and other sources for authorized users.	Yes (if BIM is a source)
InfEx-4	Secure Data Transmission	Data securely delivered to the user, including metadata for compliance logging.	No
InfEx-5	Encrypted Project Data	Data collected from sources (e.g., IoT, BIM, energy systems) encrypted for local storage.	Yes
InfEx-6	Data Categorization Schema	Rules and metadata defining how data is categorized for short-term or long-term archiving.	No

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
InfEx-7	Archived Data Logs	Logs containing metadata of archived data, including encryption and isolation status.	No
InfEx-8	Access Protocols for Archived Data	Secure protocols defining access mechanisms for archived data.	No
InfEx-9	Audit Logs and Integrity Reports	Records of data integrity checks and audits conducted for archived data.	No

7.2. UC2 - Energy monitoring and optimisation

Table 18 - UC2 conditions

Assumptions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In a building portfolio where we could find multiple process and device for satisfying the comfort of owners or occupants, and achieving to enhance energy performance and environmental sustainability
Prerequisites
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Buildings are equipped with IoT sensors and BMS, collecting the condition data of critical assets. Historical data from the assets is available Database deployed

Table 19 - UC2 Relationship to other use cases

Relationship to other use cases
Decentralized multi-source data management (UC1) Data-driven network asset management (UC3) Predictive maintenance (UC4)

Table 20 - UC2 Actors

Actors	
Grouping	Group description
Building management team	The group responsible for overseeing the operation, and management of the buildings and building portfolios. This involves strategic planning, coordination, and management of all maintenance activities to ensure that building systems and assets operate efficiently and reliably.

Monitoring Device		Enables building operators to monitor and control all critical building functions from simple interfaces, improving operational efficiency and reducing the need for manual intervention. This group is formed by IoT sensor, BMS or Management and maintenance system (CAFM/CMMS)
Application/System		Different application or system that realize an action how DSS or optimization models when they are created and tested
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description
Building Manager	Person	Oversees the overall operation of the building, ensuring all systems function properly.
Building Owner	Person	Owner of the properties or occupant that lives in the buildings
Asset Management Team	Person	Oversees the maintenance operations within building.
System operators	Person	Act as intermediaries to integrate multiple systems (e.g. HVAC, lighting, renewables, IoT sensors) within a smart building. They ensure that all systems work together efficiently, providing a holistic view of building operations.
Energy and Sustainability Team	Person	Responsible for identifying and executing energy efficiency strategies.
Developer Team	Person	The group responsible for the development of optimization/forecasting models and their deployment.
IoT/BMS	Monitoring device	Enables building operators to monitor and control all critical building functions
CAFM/CMMS	Monitoring device	Management and maintenance systems. Helps managers optimize asset utilization, including tracking their location, condition and maintenance history.
DSS	Application/System	Tool that helps in making informed decisions by analysing data, applying models and providing insights. It combines databases, analytical and other tools.

Table 21 - UC2 References

Reference type	Reference
Grant Agreement	ACCEPT platform (H2020-SC3-2018-2020 EC-3 Consumer engagement and demand response Programme under Grant Agreement - #GA:957781) [9]

Table 22 - UC2 scenarios description

N o.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
1	Data acquisition and database	Collect data from IoT sensors and BMS and organize it and its history in a database.	Monitoring Device	Initiation of data collection	Monitoring devices are installed and connection to the database	Integrating real-time sensor data, historical records, and specifications.
2	Execute Optimisation Strategies	AI and math algorithms that adjust and optimize the consumption model of building and energy community	Energy & Sustainability Team - Building Owner/Manager	Availability of sufficient data for analysis	Clean, structured data from multiple sources ready for analysis.	Optimizing models developed, providing insights into the energy consumption
3	Make Predictions	Machine learning algorithms that Forecast the usage of energy within the building.	Prediction Model	Availability of sufficient data for analysis and model already trained.	Clean, structured data and database from multiple sources ready for analysis.	Forecasting models developed, providing insights into the building energy performance
4	Show Future Analytics	Predictions and analysis of data is shown on interface to user	DSS	Predictions are made.	DSS successfully implemented, model is created and working and forecasting made.	Data insights are shown to the user for evaluation
5	Assets Integration	Assets are integrated within building by System Operators	System Operators	New or old assets in need of configuration/installation.	Assets are available and planning on where to	Assets ready to collect and send information.

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
					install them.	
6	Model Creation	Developers create prediction and optimisation models.	Algorithm Developers	Enough data available.	Data available and validated.	Prediction and Optimisation model are created.
7	Maintain Operations within Building	Assets are checked regularly in search of any kind of failure and/or problem.	Building Management Team	Failure is detected.	Assets status information is available.	Assets supervised and working fine.

Table 23 - UC2 Information exchanges

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
InfEx-1	Historical data	Past records of data, including dates, performed tasks and occupation	No
InfEx-2	Real-time data	Monitoring device and record data from each asset in the database.	No
InfEx-3	Alert profile (error data)	Automatic notifications of alert produced when certain thresholds are reached (e.g. unusually high HVAC energy consumption).	No
InfEx-4	Consumption study	Consumption comparison between buildings and energy community for the optimisation studio and the improvement of global performance	Yes
InfEx-5	Finalized optimization model	Operations scheme according to the optimization model	No
InfEx-6	Forecast future behaviour	Model forecasts future behaviour thus letting analyse patterns and act with anticipation	No
InfEx-7	Prediction visualisation	Display of the model forecasts for visualising the prediction	No
InfEx-8	Update Analytics	New analytics are done with new prediction.	No

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
InfEx-9	Alert profile (prediction)	Alerts notification when certain conditions are fulfilled (abnormal behaviour, patterns, etc...)	No
InfEx-10	Asset planning	Planification report on available asset for installation	No
InfEx-11	Assets Installation report	The assets are installed. The report has the information and localization of them	Yes if available
InfEx-12	Data availability check	Enough data for model development	No
InfEx-13	Model Deployment	Model is deployed in production for its usage	No
InfEx-14	Check Assets for failures	Report about checked asset and notification for potential or actual failures	No

Figure 12 - UC2 Scenario No. 1 - Data acquisition and database

Figure 13 – UC2 Scenario No. 2 - Execute Optimisation Strategies

Figure 14 - UC2 Scenario No. 3 - Make Predictions

Figure 15 - UC2 Scenario No. 4 - Show Future Analytics

Figure 16 - UC2 Scenario No. 5 - Assets Integration

Figure 17 - UC2 Scenario No. 6 - Model Creation

Figure 18 - UC2 Scenario No. 7 - Maintain Operations within Building

7.3. UC3 - Data-driven network asset management

Table 24 - UC3 conditions

Assumptions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In a building portfolio where we could find multiple process and devise, that are connected to the network Digital Twins, for achieving proactive prediction of asset life and anticipated failures, facilitating reliability planning and identifying common causes of asset failures.
Prerequisites
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Buildings are equipped with IoT sensors and BMS, collecting the use of smart metering data from prosumers, historical failures, network asset data, visual and IR imagery, and geo-spatial data to provide comprehensive insights into network assets To provide the network with data needed to achieve proactive prediction of asset life and anticipated failures, facilitating reliability planning and identifying common causes of asset failures.

Table 25 - UC3 relationship to other use cases

Relationship to other use cases
Decentralized multi-source data management (UC1) Energy monitoring and optimization (UC2) Predictive maintenance (UC4)

Table 26 - UC3 Actors

Actors	
Grouping	Group description
Building manager/Occupant	The group responsible for overseeing the operation, and management of the buildings and building portfolios and group of people who reside in, work in or act as prosumers who can influence and provide information to the network.
Monitoring device	Enables building operators to monitor and control all critical building functions from simple interfaces, improving operational efficiency and reducing the need for manual intervention. This group are form by IoT sensor, BMS or Management and maintenance system (CAFM/CMMS)
Application/system	Different application or system that realize an action how DSS or Digital Twin Network when it is created
Actor name	Actor type
Building manager	Person
Actor name	Actor description
Building manager	Oversees the overall operation of the building, ensuring all systems function properly.

Occupant	Person	Individuals or organisations using the building, who experience the direct effects of asset performance and can act as prosumers who can influence and provide information to the network.
Developer team	Person	Responsible for the development of the digital twin and the necessary applications for optimisation and forecasting.
Network Operators (DSOs, ESCOs)	Organization	Entities responsible for managing and operating the network infrastructure. They use the data-driven tools to optimize asset management and enhance network resilience.
IoT sensor/BMS	Device	Enables building operators to monitor and control all critical building functions
CAFM/CMMS	Device	Management and maintenance systems. Helps managers optimise asset utilization, including tracking their location, condition and maintenance history.
DSS	System	Tool that helps in making informed decisions by analysing data, applying models and providing insights. It combines databases & analytical tools
DTs	System	Virtual representations of physical network assets that integrate all relevant data to predict asset life and potential failures proactively.

Table 27 - UC3 References

Reference type	Reference
Grant Agreement	ACCEPT platform (H2020-SC3-2018-2020 EC-3 Consumer engagement and demand response Programme under Grant Agreement - #GA:957781) [9]

Table 28 - UC3 scenarios description

N o.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
1	Data acquisition and integration	Collect and integrate data from IoT sensors, BMS, cameras and manufacturer specifications.	Monitoring Device	Initiation of predict process and data collection	IoT sensors, cameras and BMS are installed and operational; historical data and manufacturer specifications are available.	Integrating real-time sensor data, historical records, and specifications
2	DT Network Creation	Create Digital Twin network, integrate a	Developer team	Availability of sufficient data for creation	Clean, structured data from	Digital Twin network created.

N o.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
		virtual model and develop a digital model representing the entire network infrastructure with decentralised implementation			multiple sources ready for analysis.	
3	Optimisation of demand management and energy trading	Implement blockchain to create a decentralised framework that allows users to participate in data and service transactions between participants and receive remuneration accordingly.	DTs	Availability of sufficient data for creation	Clean, structured data from multiple sources ready for analysis.	Optimising models developed, providing insights into demand management and energy trading
4	Prediction of Asset Life	Prediction of Asset Life focuses on analysing, optimising and predicting the useful life of each asset based on historical data and specifications in order to prevent DT network	DTs	Initiation of predict of asset Life	Historical data and asset clustering and DT Network creation	Prediction models and knowledge of asset life
5	Visualization of failure prediction and prevention	Predicting potential failures in network assets using data-driven	DSS	Significant changes in loading profiles or historical patterns showing a	DT fully synchronized with real-time asset data.	Failure alerts are generated and sent to network operators; risk-based

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
		analysis from the DT.		probable failure.		management strategies are updated based on results.
6	Critical Asset Identification and Clustering	The most critical assets for the overall operation of the network are grouped according to their importance, operational characteristics or strategic location. This allows focusing maintenance efforts and resources on the most relevant elements.	DSS	Recent failure or unusual increase in load data	Assets are integrated in DT Network	Critical assets have been identified and classified according to their criticality and the results are available for use in planning asset management strategies.
7	Implement Asset Management Strategies	Asset management strategies based on data analysis and criticality prioritization. Implementation includes preventive maintenance and corrective and infrastructure adjustments to minimize risks and optimize network performance.	Network Operator	The system generates recommendations based on prior analysis of critical assets	Previous analyses have been completed, and the critical assets are identified, and implementation tools and resources are available	Asset management strategies have been successfully implemented in the system, asset and Digital Twin data are updated reflecting the changes made.
8	Manager Flexibility Asset	Manage the operational flexibility of	Building Manager/Occupant	Detection of unexpected operational	The Digital Twin is synchronized,	Operational stability of the network

N o.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
		network assets to respond to variations in demand, network conditions or unforeseen events. To maximize the efficient use of available resources, minimising outages and ensuring network stability.		events or direct request from the operator to adjust the network load	real time data and flexibility optimization algorithms are configured	has been restored or improved.

Table 29 - UC3 Information exchanges

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
InfEx-1	Registration of asset in network	Registration of the assets to be connected to the network and the specifications.	No
InfEx-2	Existing asset data records	Initial records of existing assets, including descriptions, conditions, and locations.	No
InfEx-3	Verified asset data and updated inventory list	Updated and verified asset inventory list after reviewing and validating existing asset data.	No
InfEx-4	Geospatial modelling of the network	Geospatial data on the location and layout of network assets to identify	No
InfEx-5	Network performance reporting and analysis	Automatically generated reports that periodically analyse network performance, asset status and fault prediction.	No
InfEx-6	User registration and configuration	Prosumers and distributors (DSOs) register their IoT devices on the blockchain-based platform. Energy generation capacity, demand, tariffs, etc. are configured on the platform,	No

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
InfEx-7	Finalised optimization model	Operations scheme according to the optimization model	No
InfEx-8	Information on predicted failures	Failure predictions with criticality indexing	No
InfEx-9	Updated risk	Updated risk profiles and asset management strategies	No

Figure 19 - UC3 Scenario No. 1 - Data acquisition and integration

Figure 20 - UC3 Scenario No. 2 - DT Network Creation

Figure 21 - UC3 Scenario No. 3 - Optimisation of demand management and energy trading

Figure 22 - UC3 Scenario No. 4 - Prediction of Asset Life

Figure 23 - UC3 Scenario No. 5 - Visualization of failure prediction and prevention

Figure 24 - UC3 Scenario No. 6 - Critical Asset Identification and Clustering

Figure 25 - UC3 Scenario No. 7 - Implement Asset Management Strategies

Figure 26 - UC3 Scenario No. 8 - Manager Flexibility Asset

7.4. UC4 – Predictive maintenance

Table 30 – UC4 conditions

Assumptions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In a building portfolio where we could find multiple assets in similar types (e.g., boilers) for satisfying the demands of occupants.
Prerequisites
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Buildings are equipped with IoT sensors and BMS, collecting the condition data of critical assets. Failure and maintenance records of building assets are available through the CAFM or other systems alike.

Table 31 – UC4 relationship to other use cases

Relationship to other use cases
Decentralised multi-source data management (UC1)

Table 32 – UC4 Actors

Actors		
Grouping		Group description
Building management team		The group responsible for overseeing the operation, maintenance, and management of the buildings and building portfolios.
Occupants		The group of people who reside in or use the building, impacted by the reliability and performance of building assets.
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description
Building manager	Person	Oversees the overall operation and maintenance of the building, ensuring all systems function properly.
Maintenance manager	Person	Oversees the maintenance operations within buildings. This involves strategic planning, coordination, and management of all maintenance activities to ensure that building systems and assets operate efficiently and reliably.
Maintenance workers	Person	Conducts hand-on maintenance activities (repair or replacement), responding to prioritised maintenance schedule.
Asset management team	Person	Oversees the lifecycle of physical assets within a building or a portfolio of buildings, and ensures info about all assets are managed effectively to maximize their performance, reliability, and value over time.
IoT/BMS	Device	Enables building operators to monitor and control all critical building functions from simple interfaces,

		improving operational efficiency and reducing the need for manual intervention
CAFM	Device/System	Helps managers optimise asset utilization and maintenance workflows, including tracking their location, condition, and maintenance history
Predictive maintenance strategy	Application	Predict when facility failures might occur, allowing maintenance to be performed just in time to prevent unexpected breakdowns
Occupant	Person	Individuals or organizations using the building, who experience the direct effects of asset performance.

Table 33 - UC4 references

Reference type	Reference
Standards	BS 8210:2020 Facilities maintenance management code of practice [10]

Table 34 - UC4 scenarios description

No	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
1	Asset inventory review	Generate a comprehensive list of asset inventory for each building.	Building manager	Decision to implement predictive maintenance	Building managers have a good understanding of the buildings, or a facility management system (e.g., COBie) exists for hosting asset information.	A complete list of asset inventory for each building within the portfolio is acquired.
2	Critical asset identification	Identify key assets critical to safety, operations, and occupant comfort.	Building manager	Asset inventory acquired for the building	Comprehensive asset inventory list is available.	Critical assets are identified based on their role in the building and its usage.
3	Asset clustering	Categorise assets based on type (e.g., HVAC, electrical systems, plumbing), and group assets by	Building Manager	Identification of critical assets	Critical assets identified and categorised based on their type and operational conditions.	Assets are grouped into clusters to enable efficient monitoring and maintenance strategies, for

No	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
		operational conditions (e.g., high-use areas, harsh environments).				solving data scarce issues.
4	Data acquisition and integration	Collect and integrate data from IoT sensors, BMS, historical maintenance records (CAFM), and manufacturer specifications.	Building Manager and Maintenance Manager	Initiation of predictive maintenance data collection	IoT sensors and BMS are installed and operational; historical data and manufacturer specifications are available.	Comprehensive dataset gathered, integrating real-time sensor data, historical records, and specifications.
5	Asset deterioration modelling	Machine learning algorithms are applied to model asset deterioration patterns and predict failures and maintenance needs.	Maintenance Manager	Availability of sufficient data for analysis in the specific asset cluster	Clean, structured data from multiple sources ready for analysis.	Predictive models developed, providing insights into potential failures and maintenance needs.
6	Maintenance scheduling	Schedule maintenance tasks based on predictive insights to minimise disruption and ensure asset reliability.	Maintenance managers	Completion of predictive models	Prioritised list of maintenance tasks based on failure predictions; maintenance resources are available.	Maintenance tasks are scheduled at optimal times, minimising disruption to building operations.
7	Maintenance execution	Deploy maintenance teams to perform repairs or replacements according to the scheduled tasks.	Maintenance workers	Maintenance schedule finalised	Maintenance teams are assigned tasks based on the schedule.	Maintenance tasks are completed, reducing downtime and ensuring asset reliability.

Table 35 - UC4 Information exchanges

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
InfEx-1	Existing asset data records	Initial records of existing assets, including descriptions, conditions, and locations.	No in most cases
InfEx-2	Verified asset data and updated inventory list	Updated and verified asset inventory list after reviewing and validating existing asset data.	Suggested, but not necessarily
InfEx-3	Defined criteria for critical asset identification	Criteria set to determine which assets are critical to building operations and safety.	No
InfEx-4	List of critical assets based on defined criteria	A list of assets identified as critical according to the previously defined criteria.	No
InfEx-5	List of assets grouped by types and operational conditions	Assets categorised by type (e.g., HVAC, plumbing) and grouped by their operational conditions (e.g., high-use areas).	No
InfEx-6	Real-time IoT sensor and BMS data	Continuous data from IoT sensors and Building Management Systems monitoring asset performance and environmental conditions.	No, relational or nonrelational databases, but the integration relies on BIM
InfEx-7	Historical maintenance data	Past records of maintenance activities, including dates, performed tasks, and outcomes.	No, relational or nonrelational databases, but the integration relies on BIM
InfEx-8	Manufacturer specifications and guidelines	Technical documentation provided by manufacturers detailing maintenance procedures, specifications, and operational guidelines.	No, documents, but the integration relies on BIM
InfEx-9	Finalised maintenance schedule	The detailed schedule for upcoming maintenance tasks, organized to minimize disruption and ensure asset reliability.	No, mostly tabular format

Figure 27 - UC4 - Scenario No. 1 - Asset inventory review

Figure 28 - UC4 Scenario No. 2 - Critical asset identification

Figure 29 - UC4 Scenario No. 3 - Asset clustering

Figure 30 – UC4 Scenario No. 4 – Data acquisition and integration

Figure 31 – UC4 Scenario No. 5 – Asset deterioration modelling

Figure 32 – UC4 Scenario No. 6 – Maintenance scheduling

7.5. UC5 – Risk, resilience and biodiversity nexus

Table 36 – UC5 conditions

Assumptions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As much as possible specific input data will be available to use limited generic / proxy data Use case condition for assessing a building’s robustness, resilience, and service level with limited and generic proxy data could involve evaluating structural performance in an event where only partial building information is available. The available input data may include basic geometric parameters (e.g., number of stories, floor area, and structural system type), material properties inferred from regional construction practices, and generic occupancy data based on building function (e.g., residential). Lacking specific design details, the assessment would rely on standardized fragility curves, empirical damage models. Indirect loss estimation may use industry benchmarks for downtime, repair costs, and economic impacts based on building type and exposure.
Prerequisites
Input data mandatory for indicators’ calculation will be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building data available and updated (DT model, geometry, energy consumption in real time and forecast); climate hazard historical data.

Table 37 – UC5 relationship to other use cases

Relationship to other use cases
Decentralised multi-source data management (UC1) Energy monitoring and optimization (UC 2) Renovation planning and design (UC6) Technoeconomic investment planning for property owners (UC7) Boost of green energy investments by market actors (UC 8)

Table 38 – UC5 actors (Human)

Actors		
Grouping		Human actor
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description
Client: property owners, city managers	Italian State (Agenzia del Demanio)	The client is the ultimate decision-maker, providing the project scope, budget, and desired outcomes. ADD is the manager on behalf of the Italian state
Contractor	Agenzia del Demanio (ADD)	The contractor is responsible for executing the project, managing the construction team, and ensuring adherence to the design and budget.

Auditor	Private Entity	A building auditor is a professional who specializes in assessing a building's compliance with regulations, standards, and quality requirements.
Designer / Architect team	Private Architecture Studio	The designer/architect team creates the building's design, incorporating BIM models to visualize and coordinate the renovation.
Engineering team	Private Engineering firm	The engineering team ensures the building's structural integrity, HVAC systems, electrical systems, safety and sustainability according to the European Construction Products Regulation (CPR) and to the national requirements
Regulatory entities	Superintendent of Fine Arts, Italian Construction Codes, Eurocodes, Regional Codes, Regional Urban regulations, Regional Environmental regulations Fire safety regulations	Regulatory entities provide guidelines and regulations that must be followed throughout the project, such as building codes, environmental standards, and energy efficiency requirements.

Table 39 - UC5 actors (technical)

Actors		
Grouping		Tool actor
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) generic databases, e.g. Ecolnvent	LCA expert from private firm	These databases gather the different generic process data that will feed the inventory phase of the LCA
Construction Products LCA databases, e.g. INIES	LCA expert from private firm	These databases gather the results of the construction products LCA (in standard files such as the EPDs) that will feed the Building LCA
Land Use Occupation data, e.g. CORINE Land Cover	Regional Urban codes	dataset on the land cover and land use according to thematic classes (e.g. forested area. It serves a multitude of users for different applications such as: environmental monitoring, land use planning, climate

		<p>change assessments, risk and emergency management</p> <p>Using GIS maps is possible to see the land use of a given territory, environmental monitoring, classes, woodlands, environmental monitoring, land use planning, climate change assessments, risk and emergency management</p>
Building materiality models, e.g. TyPy	Model & database	Model of the building materials and database that gather information on the types of the materials that are used in a building according to a specific/standard structure
LCA models	database/inventory	phases scheme models that will feed LCA tools to carry out the environmental assessment based on the life cycle approach
Resilience Engineering Platform	Method/Model	The tool provides a solution for assessing and enhancing the resilience of assets across their lifecycle. Integrating risk management, crisis management, and business continuity into asset management, the platform enables users to model and quantify risks, analyze hazards, and evaluate impacts through scenario-based assessments. It delivers actionable insights via detailed outputs like loss curves and resilience indicators, supporting data-driven decision-making for resource allocation and investment prioritization. The platform has specialized applications for maintenance planning, emergency response, and hazard mitigation
Urban Heat Island (UHI) assessment models	Method/Model	Models that describe the UHI phenomena/risk; they feed the UHI tools that allow the performance assessment of different solutions to assure the resilience to these kind of risk
Ecological models	Method/Model	The ecological model that will be used in the framework of the WILSON project allows to assess the ability of different spaces to support biodiversity. This model categorizes land use into 41 distinct typologies, such as green spaces with or without trees, wetlands, extensive green roofs etc. By

		characterizing land use in this detailed manner, the model aims to identify which types of spaces are most conducive to fostering biodiversity. This approach helps in understanding how different land use practices can either enhance or diminish the ecological value of an area, ultimately guiding efforts to promote biodiversity in urban environments.
Hybrid models, e.g. HIBOU	Method / Model	Model that considers <i>in situ</i> and <i>ex situ</i> environmental impacts (e.g. biodiversity) of the building or district
LCA generic tools, e.g. Simapro	SimaPro© GABI©	Tool that calculates the environmental indicators (LCA based) for generic process and products
Building LCA tools, e.g. Cometh, ComEnv, Biodiv-Ex	SimaPro© GABI©	Tool that calculates the environmental indicators (LCA based, such as energy, carbon, ex-situ biodiversity) at building scale
District LCA tools, e.g. UrbanPrint	Tool	Tool that calculates the environmental indicators (LCA based, such as energy, carbon, ex-situ biodiversity) at district scale
UHI assessment tool, e.g. EnviBatie	Tool	Tool that calculates the UHI indicators
Ecological/Local or <i>in situ</i> Biodiversity tools, e.g. Biodiv – in, BAFh	Tool	Tool that calculates the environmental/ biodiversity indicators specific to the building or district site. To be confirmed in the relevant activities that will implement the methodologies of resilience tools.

Table 40 - UC5 references

Reference type	Reference	Impact on use case
Regulation	CPR – European Construction Products Regulation [11]	Requirements concerning the construction products at building scale
EU standard	EN 15804 [12]	European Method for Construction Product LCA
EU standard	EN 15978 [13]	European Method for Building LCA
ISO standard	ISO 16739-1:2024 [14]	International standard for information used in BIM

Reference type	Reference	Impact on use case
Product Category Rules (PCR)	C-PCR-029 [15]	Specifications and Guidelines for EPD Creation.

Table 41 - UC5 scenarios description

N o.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Pre-condition	Post-condition
1	Asset, Context, and Hazards Characterization	Input data gathering for each demo site/pilot (incl. data from national regulatory entities) - Definition of the proxy / generic data to be use for the calculation step based on the state of the art	Demo site/ Pilots responsible/Technical staff	Input data: (plan views – environmental studies – regional and national codes – event register) Historical behaviour; ESRI; Regional Codes; Maps; Event register;	Asset characterization ; Definition of relevant hazards and threats scenarios
2	Risk, Resilience, Carbon and Biodiversity Assessment	Create as-is model and to-be model	Technical staff	Proxi/ generic data definition for the unavailable input data	
3	Data-Driven Decision Support	Once the state of the art has been evaluated, improvements are implemented to evaluate the asset's behaviour	Technical staff	State of art results; <i>ante-operam</i> vulnerability index, impact assessment calculations	Creation of alternative models to improve pilot/demo performance
4	Use Case-Specific Applications	mitigation of the risks arising from hazards, proposing actions aimed at improving KPI related to the use case	Technical staff	Mitigation of flood (e.g. riverbank works, barriers outflow system improvement), heat wave (e.g.: tele-heat system further protection and seismic (e.g. isolators) risks	Creation of alternative models to improve pilot/demo performance Development of alternative models to enhance pilot/demo performance

Table 42 - UC5 Information exchanges

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
1	BIM Model	Bim model developed with Autodesk Revit for all disciplines (architectural, structural, MEP) - the information extracted from BIM was used to generate the calculation models for each discipline as well as the computation of the works that were used to identify the total amount of work	All the information comes from the BIM model
2	Excel file	Input data (cf. T4.1) for each building of the assessed pilot	

Figure 33 – UC5 Scenario No. 1 - Asset, context and hazards characterisation

Figure 34 - UC5 Scenario No. 2 - Risk, resilience, carbon and biodiversity assessment

7.6. UC6 - Renovation planning and design

Table 43 - UC6 conditions

Assumptions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A collaboration tool exists to support the renovation design process • A building stock Database system is available to retrieve data about the renovated building • product catalog repositories exist and are accessible in a standard way • Various simulation tools from Wilson are available • A digital twin platform exists to data along the renovation design process
Prerequisites
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inputs data needed for the energy, environmental & economic assessment of the WILSON demo sites are available: building geometry, material description (see the diagram)

Table 44 - UC6 relationship to other UCs

Relationship to other use cases
Decentralised multi-source data management (UC1)
Energy monitoring and optimisation (UC2)
Risk, resilience and biodiversity nexus (UC5)
Technoeconomic investment planning for property owners (UC7)

Table 45 - UC6 Actors (Human)

Actors		
Grouping		Human actor
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description
Building Owner	Person	The client is the ultimate decision-maker, providing the project scope, budget, and desired outcomes.
Contractor	Person	The contractor is responsible for executing the project, managing the construction team, and ensuring adherence to the design and budget.
Auditor	Person	A building auditor is a professional who specializes in assessing a building's compliance with regulations, standards, and quality requirements. They conduct thorough inspections of various building components, including structural elements, electrical systems, HVAC systems, and energy efficiency measures.
Designer / Architect team	Person(s)	The designer/architect team creates the building's design, incorporating BIM models to visualize and coordinate the renovation.
Engineering team	Person(s)	The engineering team ensures the building's structural integrity, HVAC systems, electrical systems, safety and sustainability according to the European Construction Products Regulation (CPR) and to the national requirements
Regulatory entities	Person(s)	Regulatory entities provide guidelines and regulations that must be followed throughout the project, such as building codes, environmental standards, and energy efficiency requirements.

Table 46 - UC6 Actors (technical)

Actors		
Grouping		Technical actor
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description
Thermal Simulation tools	Application/System	Thermal simulation tools analyse a building's energy performance, helping designers optimize insulation, HVAC systems, and overall energy consumption.
BIM on-site acquiring services	Monitoring Devices	BIM on-site acquiring services leverage BIM models to capture and manage construction data, ensuring accuracy and reducing errors.
Building stock DB	Database	A building stock database is a centralized repository of information on buildings in a Country. It contains data such as building characteristics, energy performance, and renovation projects. This database is used by various stakeholders, including architects,

		<p>engineers, government officials, and researchers. It provides valuable insights into the building stock and supports sustainable development initiatives. The database is continuously updated with new data and is a valuable resource for understanding the built environment.</p>
Collaboration suite	Application/Services	<p>Collaboration suites facilitate real-time communication and collaboration among project teams, improving coordination and reducing delays. Collaboration can be made around a BIM CDE that is a centralized platform that manages and shares project information, including BIM models, documentation, and collaboration tools, throughout the building lifecycle</p>
Products catalogues	Databases	<p>Products catalogues offer a centralized or decentralized repository of building materials, components, and specifications, simplifying the procurement process and ensuring consistency in design and construction.</p>
Building Digital twin	Model	<p>A building digital twin is a virtual representation of a physical building that mirrors its design, construction, and operation. It leverages advanced technologies such as BIM, IoT, and AI to simulate real-world conditions and provide valuable insights. In the construction business, digital twins can be used to optimize design, improve construction efficiency, monitor performance, and identify potential issues before they occur. By creating a digital replica of a building, construction professionals can make data-driven decisions and enhance the overall project lifecycle.</p>
Resilience Engineering Platform	Tool	<p>RINA's tool provides a solution for assessing and enhancing the resilience of assets across their lifecycle. Integrating risk management, crisis management, and business continuity into asset management, the platform enables users to model and quantify risks, analyze hazards, and evaluate impacts through scenario-based assessments. It delivers actionable insights via detailed outputs like loss curves and resilience indicators, supporting data-driven decision-making for resource allocation and investment prioritization. The platform has specialized</p>

	applications for maintenance planning, emergency response, and hazard mitigation.
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Table 47 - UC6 References

Reference type	Reference	Impact on use case
Regulation	CPR – European Construction Products Regulation [11]	Requirements
EU standard	EN 15804 [12]	Method
EU standard	EN 15978 [13]	Method
ISO standard	ISO 16739-1 :2024 [14]	International standard for information used in BIM
Guide	Guide to Cost-Benefit Analysis of Investment Projects [16]	Method

Table 48 - UC6 Scenarios description

N o.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
1	Project scope, Budget and Contractors	Purely human activity: envisioning the renovation project, defining the scope and objectives, allocating the budget and identifying the contractors.	Building Owners	New energy and environmental sustainability regulations/st andards.	Availability of Building assessment (plus energy and environmental performance); client objectives defined; availability of resources (budget, team).	Project scope and agreements between stakeholders.
2	Gather as-is data	Activity of collecting and storing documents, BIM data, and any information describing the initial state of the building to be renovated	Building Owners	Decision to proceed with renovation planning.	Availability and accessibility of documents, BIM files and information.	As-is data repository available (PDHs and Continium interconnected)

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
		(as-is). Provided in UCI – Scenario 1				
3	Create as-is model	The data collected on the original building is used to create the first digital twin model, which represents the as-built situation and is used in subsequent processes.	Designers (Team of Specialists – Architects, engineers) and technical partners.	As-is data collection process completed	As-is data available and usable as input to the modelling tool.	Creation of a preliminary as-is DT model of the building.
4	Improve As-Is Model &	Improve the level of detail of the digital twin to capture more accurate information about the existing building. Data from building stock databases and product catalogues can be used to improve the initial description of the situation.	Designers (Team of Specialists – Architects, engineers)	Preliminary as-is DT Model not sufficiently precise.	Availability of preliminary as-is DT Model	A more accurate as-is DT model, capable of representing the characteristics of the building with a high level of detail.
5	Design of possible alternatives	Different renovation alternatives can be designed using different	Designers (Team of Specialists – Architec	As-is DT Model available and of high quality	As-is DT Model and material passports need to be completed; design team ready to	Create To-Be DT models representative of different renovation scenarios.

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
		products from product catalogues. Different passports can be created for these different alternatives.	ts, engineers)		consider renovation solutions.	
6	Process Baseline, Alternatives & Update Passports	Various simulation tools use DT semantic descriptions and the various values from the created passports to calculate and store KPIs for the "as-is" baseline situation and for the various alternatives that have been created.	Designers (Team of Specialists – Architects, engineers)	Creation of To-Be renovation alternatives	Availability of simulation tools to assess performance indicators (energy assessment, environmental impact and economic benefits - also KPIs related to CBA)	KPIs available both for baseline (as-is) and for alternatives (To-Be) conditions.
7	Validate Concept: Choose an Alternative	Displaying calculated KPIs, enabling the technical team and client to make an informed decision on the preferred renovation alternative.	Designers (Team of Specialists – Architects, engineers) and Clients	KPI calculation and visualization	The client and the team have a clear understanding of baseline and alternative performances as well as the associated costs and environmental impacts.	Renovation alternative is selected, considering technical, economic, and environmental targets.
8	Validate project	Regulatory bodies can validate the refurbishment	Regulatory Entities	Selection of the renovation alternative and	Finalized renovation plan with necessary compliance	Project validation is complete, and required

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
		nt project and issue all necessary permits.		preparation of necessary documentation for validation.	reports, including adherence to local and EU standards/references.	permits are issued to proceed with the technical design phase.
9	Technical Design Phase	A more detailed technical design is created for the chosen renovation option, preparing for the execution phase	Designers (Team of Specialists – Architects, engineers)	Renovation project is validated, and permits are secured.	Approved renovation plan, permits, and detailed inputs from the selected alternative.	A comprehensive and detailed technical design is prepared, ready for execution in the construction/renovation phase.

Table 49 - UC6 Information exchanges

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
Inf/ex-1	Project objectives and constrains	Clear understanding of main project objectives and possible constrains (including renovations goals, sustainability targets and available budget).	No
Inf/ex-2	Contractor selection	Identification of the contractors in charge of developing the renovation activities.	No
Inf/ex-3	Building Technical Data	Access to relevant building information, models, data relevant to the development of the as-built model.	Yes
Inf/ex-4	As-is Model development	Develop an initial as-is DT Model based on existing information and data.	
Inf/ex-5	Saving of as-is DT Model	Ensure that the as-is DT model is correctly stored in the identified repository space.	No
Inf/ex-6	As-is DT model assessment	Identify missing, outdated or misaligned information.	Yes
Inf/ex-7	To-be model development	Development of the final model, considering the evaluation of alternatives performance	Yes

Figure 35 - UC6 Scenario No. 1 - Project scope, Budget and Contractors

Figure 36 - UC6 Scenario No. 3 - Create as-is model

Figure 37 - UC6 Scenario No. 4 - Improve as-is model and create passports

Figure 38 - UC6 Scenario No. 5 - Design possible alternatives

Figure 39 - UC6 Scenario No. 6 - Process baseline, alternatives & update passports

Figure 40 - UC6 Scenario No. 7 - Validate concept: choose an alternative

Figure 41 - UC6 Scenario No. 8 - Validate project

Figure 42 - UC6 Scenario No. 9 - Technical design phase

7.7. UC7 - Technoeconomic investment planning for property owners

Table 50- UC7 conditions

Assumptions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buildings and building portfolio need to improve their performance • Investors and owners require financial modelling and investment scenarios
Prerequisites
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is reliable data on building performance • The property ownership acknowledges the need for building improvements for better performance • The investors and owners have agreed a ROI threshold

Table 51 - UC7 relationship to other use cases

Relationship to other use cases
Renovation planning and design (UC6)
Boost of green energy investment by market actors (UC8)
Energy monitoring and optimisation (UC2)

Table 52 - UC7 actors

Actors		
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description
Occupants (workers and patients)	Person	Individuals or organizations using the building, who experience the direct effects of asset performance.
Building/Property owners	Business actor	Decision-makers evaluating financial and environmental benefits of renovation projects
Financial Institutions	Business actor	Stakeholders providing capital, requiring ROI, and compliance with green finance criteria
Building managers	System Actor	Responsible for providing baseline data on building performance and operational costs
IoT/BMS	System actor	Sources for real-time building performance data, such as IoT sensors and energy meters
Service providers	System actor	The group of people who provide the assets (e.g. for the hospital to run)
Developer Team	System actor	The group responsible for the development of the investment planning tool

Table 53 - UC7 references

Reference type	Reference	Impact on use case
Standard	ISO14044 [17]	Describes several checks to test whether data and procedures support conclusions for LCC evaluation

Table 54 - UC7 scenarios description

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
1	Assessment of the building	Assess existing building performance	Building owner, energy/financial analysts	Decision to seek investment/ decision to improve building performance	Complete building performance data	A complete assessment of the existing building performance is completed
2	Identification of investment	Identify all relevant possible	Building owner, financial	Data on performance of	Full list of viable	A complete list of feasible/relev

No	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
	Investment opportunities	Investment opportunities that can be tailored to the needs of the construction of new buildings	Institutions, energy/financial analysts	The building acquired	Investment options	Investment opportunities are acquired
3	Cost-benefit analysis	Conduct Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) to assess financial implications	Building owner, energy/financial analysts	Data on performance of the building acquired	Investment and cost data ready	The assessment of financial implications of the building is completed
4	LCC evaluation	Evaluate Life Cycle Cost implication for long-term viability	Building owner, energy/financial analysts	Data on the performance of the building acquired	Investment and environmental impact data available	The assessment of environmental, financial and long-term viability of the building is completed
5	Financial modelling	Simulate different investment scenarios with financial modelling	Developer team, energy/financial analysts	Identification of investment opportunities and LCC and CBA analysis completion	Investment and market data available	Financial modelling simulations with different investment scenarios are completed

Table 55 - UC7 information exchanges

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
Inf/ex-1	Baseline energy consumption	Current building energy use data for establishing starting point	Yes
Inf/ex-2	Renovation costs	Projected costs of each proposed renovation scenario	No
Inf/ex-3	ROI and payback calculations	Calculated return on investment and payback periods	No

Inf/ex-4	Environmental impact projections	Estimated carbon and energy reductions per renovation scenario	Yes
Inf/ex-5	Financial model data	Assumptions, calculations, and projections for scenario analysis	No

Figure 43 - UC7 scenario No. 1 - Assessment of the building

Figure 44 - UC7 Scenario No. 2 - Identification of investment opportunities

Figure 45 - UC7 Scenario No. 3 - Cost-benefit analysis

Figure 46 - UC7 Scenario No. 4 - Life Cycle Cost evaluation

Figure 47 - UC7 Scenario No. 5 - Financial modelling

7.8. UC8 - Boost of green energy investments by market actors

Table 56 – UC8 conditions

Assumptions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A building portfolio containing various assets and smart meters. The Energy Monitoring Tool accesses data from these assets and the smart meter via the data space. It provides key functionalities - including monitoring, optimization, simulation, and network capability analysis - to support decision-making, optimize operations, and guide investments.
Prerequisites
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building equipped with a range of assets and smart meters. The data of the assets and smart meters is accessible through an API, providing connectivity and management. The data of external sources (e.g. weather, open property information) is accessible through an API. Data owners give their allowance to access and analyse their data.

Table 57 – UC8 Relationship to other use cases

Relationship to other use cases
Decentralised multi-source data management (UC1)
Energy Monitoring and Optimization (UC2)
Data-Driven Network Asset Management (UC3)

Table 58 – UC8 Actors

Actors		
Actor name	Actor type	Actor description
Building Manager	Person	Oversees the overall operation of the building, ensuring all systems function properly.
Building Owner	Person	Owner of the properties or occupant that lives in the buildings
Asset Management Team	Person	Oversees the maintenance operations within building.
System operators	Person	Act as intermediaries to integrate multiple systems (e.g. HVAC, lighting, renewables, IoT sensors) within a smart building. They ensure that all systems work together efficiently, providing a holistic view of building operations.
DSO	Person (Organisation)	The Distribution System Operators (DSOs) act as energy provider and grid operator. Monitors and optimizes (operation, investments) the energy grid on a community level.

Assets	Monitoring device	Enables Energy Monitoring System to monitor and control energy consumption and production
Smart Meters	Monitoring device	Enables Energy Monitoring System to monitor energy consumption and production
Data Space	Data Space infrastructure	Enables to access the data provided by the assets and smart meters and to control assets and smart meters functions
Energy Monitoring System	Application/System	Tool that monitors energy consumption and production. It helps in making informed decisions by analysing data by applying AI, algorithms and providing insights.

Table 59 – UC8 references

Reference type	Reference	Impact on use case
Guide	IDS-RAM (International Data Spaces Reference Architecture Model) [17]	Framework used for the development of the data space infrastructure

Table 60 – UC8 Scenarios description

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
1	Data access and collection using a data space infrastructure	Access and collect data from assets and smart meters via a data space infrastructure.	Data space infrastructure	Initiation of data collection	Assets and smart meters are connected to the data space	Provide the Energy Monitoring System with the required data
2	Energy consumption and production monitoring	Collect the energy consumption and production data from the assets and smart meters via the data space	Energy Monitoring System	Initiation of the data monitoring	Data from the assets and smart meters are accessible via the data space	Data from the assets and smart meters is stored in the Energy Monitoring System
3	Energy consumption and production forecasting	Forecast future energy consumption and production,	Energy Monitoring System	Initiation of forecast	Monitored data, and external data (e.g. weather)	Forecast for energy consumption and production

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
		based on the monitored data			is accessible	(e.g. for the next day)
4	Self-consumption optimization	AI and math algorithms that adjust and optimize the self-consumption of energy on a building and energy community level	Energy Monitoring System	Availability of sufficient data for the analysis	Data from multiple assets ready for analysis	Optimizing models, providing insight into self-consumption strategies
5	Grid load simulation	AI and math algorithms that simulate the grid load on an energy community level based on the energy consumption of one or more buildings	Energy Monitoring System	Availability of sufficient data for the simulation	Data from smart meters, and multiple assets ready for analysis	Simulation of the grid load on an energy community level based on the energy consumption of one or more buildings
6	Network capability metrics provision	AI and math algorithms that provide network capability metrics to optimize operations and guide investments in new assets	Energy Monitoring System	Availability of sufficient data (e.g. from assets, optimization, simulation) for the calculation of network capability metrics	Data from smart meters, and multiple assets ready for analysis	Network capability metrics to optimize operations and guide investments in new assets
7	Show decision-support	Results of the Energy Monitoring System are shown in a GUI to provide decision-support	Energy Monitoring System	Network capability metrics are calculated	Energy Monitoring System is working, and network capability metrics are calculated	Results of the Energy Monitoring System are shown to the user for decision-making
8	Self-consumption	Decision-making to	System Operator	Network capabilities	Network capability	Self-consumption

No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
	operations optimization	optimize self-consumption operations		metrics are shown to the user	metrics are available and displayed	operations optimization based on the insights from the calculations
9	Grid operations optimizations	Decision-making to optimize self-consumption operations	DSO	Network capabilities are shown to the user	Network capability metrics are available and displayed	Grid operations optimization (e.g. peak shaving) based on the insights from the calculations
10	Investment guidance	Decision-making to guide investments	DSO	Network capabilities are shown to the user	Network capability metrics are available and displayed	Investments (e.g. optimization & trading, cost for balancing energy) are made based on the insights from the calculations

Table 61 – UC8 Information exchanges

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
InfEx-1	Asset ID	The ID is a unique identifier of an asset that is connected to the data space	No
InfEx-2	Asset data	Data from the assets that is relevant to be sent to the Energy Monitoring System	No
InfEx-3	Simulation parameter	Parameters for the grid load simulation, e.g, community size	No
InfEx-4	Results of the Energy Monitoring System	Results of the Energy Monitoring System that are shown in a GUI to provide decision-support	No
InfEx-5	Network capability metrics	Network capability metrics to optimize operations and guide investments in new assets	No

Information exchanged, ID	Name of information	Description of information exchanged	Information from BIM?
InfEx-6	Consumption optimizations recommendations	Self-consumption operations optimization recommendations based on the insights from the calculations	No
InfEx-7	Grid optimizations recommendations	Grid operations optimization recommendations based on the insights from the calculations	No
InfEx-8	investment recommendations	New investments recommendations based on the insights from the calculations	No
InfEx-9	External data	External data sources, e.g. weather data, open property information	No
InfEx-10	Forecast parameters	Parameters for the consumption and production forecast, e.g. day for forecast	No

Figure 48 – UC8 Scenario No. 1 - Data access and collection using a data space infrastructure

Figure 49 – UC8 Scenario No. 2 - Energy consumption and production monitoring

Figure 50 – UC8 Scenario No. 3 - Energy consumption and production forecasting

Figure 51 – UC8 Scenario No. 4 - Self-consumption optimization

Figure 52 – UC8 Scenario No. 5 - Grid load simulation

Figure 53 – UC8 Scenario No. 6 - Network capability metrics provision

Figure 54 – UC8 Scenario No. 7 - Show decision-support

Figure 55 – UC8 Scenario No. 8 - Self-consumption operations optimization

Figure 56 – UC8 Scenario No. 9 - Grid operations optimizations

Figure 57 – UC8 Scenario No. 10 – Investment guidance

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